

Оценка на свойствата на материалните аспекти на вътрешноприсъщата бариера пред разпространението на реакторен плутоний при многократно рециклиране в реактори с вода под налягане

Ивайло Найденов, Калин Филипов

Плутоният е един от основните ядрени материали, допринасящ към риска от нерегламентираното им разпространение. Факторите, свързани с материалните свойства, имат основен принос към формирането на т.нар. вътрешноприсъща бариера пред разпространението. В настоящата статия е разгледано изменението на тези аспекти в случая на многократно рециклиране на плутония в реактори с вода под налягане като е направено сравнение с два референтни горивни цикъла.

Ключови думи: плутоний, неразпространение, ядрени горивни цикли

Change of the Quality of the Material Aspects of the Intrinsic Proliferation Barrier of Reactor-Grade Plutonium in the Case of Multiple Recycle in Pressurised Water Reactors

Ivaylo Naydenov, Kalin Filipov

Plutonium is among the nuclear materials with major contribution to the proliferation risk. The factors related to the material's properties have the main role in forming the intrinsic proliferation barrier. The current article examines the change of those aspects in the case of multiple recycle of plutonium in pressurized water reactors. A comparison with two reference fuel cycles has been done as well.

Keywords: plutonium, non-proliferation, nuclear fuel cycles

Introduction

The relevance of the problems, associated with nuclear materials' non-proliferation is defined by the following circumstances: (1) nuclear power is considered to be a dual purpose technology [10,11] and (2) the probability for proliferation creates certain obstacles before nuclear power's development in terms of creating negative perception of nuclear technology [6]. Proliferation resistance is among the core principles of nuclear power development and is an objective that should be fulfilled by advanced fuel cycles [7,8]. Proliferation resistance also represents a necessary condition set forth by the European commission that needs to be met, in order the future advancement of nuclear energy in the European Union to be guaranteed [5]. It is thought that proliferation of nuclear materials is one of the most important problems standing before the future progress of nuclear energy [13].

The main concerns about possible proliferation risk increase are based on the global plutonium inventory that is estimated to be increasing at a rate of about 60 tonnes per annum [4]. Plutonium is considered to be among the most important materials from non-proliferation perspective [13]. In order to define the level of civilian plutonium's usability for nuclear explosive device construction, it is necessary to analyse those properties of the material that could make it suitable for non-civilian applications. Most often, the attributes linked to material's proliferation resistance are the bare critical mass of a sphere, its decay heat, the spontaneous neutron emission, and the radiological barrier [4,6].

Generally, three main plutonium management options can be outlined: (1) indefinite-term storage in facilities with high physical protection levels; (2) reprocessing, MOX fuel manufacturing

and burning in power reactors; and (3) immobilisation in glass or ceramic matrix. The burning of plutonium in MOX fuel form and the metal's immobilisation are considered the two least problematic options for plutonium management [9]. Currently, the main approach for plutonium's energy utilization is MOX fuel manufacturing and its usage in thermal and, to a considerably lesser extent, in fast neutron reactors [21]. The scheme of the classic single plutonium recycle in PWR is shown on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Partially closed fuel cycle with single plutonium recycle in pressurised water reactor, adapted from [17]

An alternative fuel cycle option that would allow multiple recycling of plutonium in PWRs is the usage of MOX fuel that is manufactured by blending the plutonium with enriched instead of depleted uranium. That concept is known as MOX Enriched Uranium Support (MOX/EUS) or MIX. Unlike traditional MOX where the depleted uranium is used as a matrix material and the plutonium oxide is the main provider of fissile nuclei, in MIX fuels PuO_2 acts as a secondary source of fissile isotopes. In addition, the enriched uranium would enable multiple plutonium recycles in PWRs because it would compensate the loss of reactivity due to the deteriorating plutonium isotopic composition caused by the multiple consecutive irradiations [16,20]. This concept is illustrated on Fig. 2. On Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 the following abbreviations are adopted: UOX – uranium oxide fuel; PWR – pressurised water reactor; SNF – spent nuclear fuel; RAW – radioactive waste; HLW – high-level waste; ILW – intermediate-level waste; LLW – low-level waste; FP – fission products; MA – minor actinides; HM – heavy metal; MOX – mixed oxide fuel.

Fig. 2 Partially closed fuel cycle with multiple plutonium recycles in pressurised water reactor, using the MOX/EUS concept, adapted from [17]

Objectives, input data, and methodology

In the current paper the effects of plutonium multiple recycling on material's proliferation resistance properties have been examined. The analysed fuel cycle realizes four-fold plutonium

recycle using MIX fuel, the plutonium after the fourth recycle being set for 300 years decay. The multiple recycle option is compared to two reference cycles: once-through fuel cycle and single plutonium recycle using MOX fuel.

The stages of the MIX fuel cycle are as follows: first, enriched uranium oxide fuel is loaded in a reference PWR (1000 MW gross electric power output, 33% gross unit thermodynamic efficiency) and irradiated for 1241 EFPD, then the spent fuel is discharged (that is the zero recycle or R0) and cooled down for 10 years. At that point the plutonium is extracted and used for manufacturing the MIX fuel for the first recycling. The MIX fuel is also irradiated in the reference PWR for 1241 EFPD. Those steps are repeated three more times. After discharging the fuel from the fourth recycle (R4), it is set for 300 years decay. The overall fuel cycle duration thus becomes 356 years, considering the moment of uranium fuel discharge as Year 0. The refuelling outages are not taken into account.

For comparability, the length of the reference cases is also set at 356 years. In the once-through cycle, the spent fuel is set for 356 years decay right after initial discharge. In the MOX recycle case, the discharged UOX fuel cools down for ten years; then MOX fuel is manufactured and irradiated for 1241 EFPD. The spent MOX fuel then cools down for 342 years adding up to 356 years total fuel cycle length. The fuel cycles' stages are illustrated on Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Examined fuel cycles and timeline of their stages; above: multiple plutonium recycles; in the middle: no recycle; below: single plutonium recycle

The qualities of plutonium's material barrier are assessed using the 'Figure of Merit' criteria. The 'Figure of Merit' methodology is used to assess the material's usability for the construction of a nuclear explosive device by a nation or a sub-national group. The methodology uses two criteria, FOM_1 and FOM_2 , in order to assess the material. They are calculated using Eqs. (1) and (2). These criteria include several intrinsic factors such as bare critical mass M , spontaneous neutron fraction S , decay heat DH , and dose rate DR . The first criterion assesses the material's usability when the explosive yield is of little importance and pre-detonation is not an issue, while the second criterion assesses the case when nominal yield and storability are desirable [2,3]. This effectively means that FOM_1 criterion does not take into account the effects of the spontaneous neutron emission, while FOM_2 could be used to assess the impact of even plutonium isotopes on the material barrier. The present analysis has been carried out using the algorithm applied in [15].

$$FOM_1 = 1 - \lg \left[\frac{M}{800} + \frac{M \cdot DH}{4500} + \frac{M}{50} \cdot \left(\frac{DR}{500} \right)^{\frac{1}{\lg 2}} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$FOM_1 = 1 - \lg \left[\frac{M}{800} + \frac{M \cdot DH}{4500} + \frac{M \cdot S}{6.8 \cdot 10^6} + \frac{M}{50} \cdot \left(\frac{DR}{500} \right)^{\frac{1}{\lg 2}} \right] \quad (2)$$

where: M is the bare critical mass (BCM) of a sphere, kg;

DH – the specific decay heat, W/kg;

S – the spontaneous neutron fraction, (n·kg)/s;

DR – the dose rate of 20% of the BCM at a distance from the source of 1 m, rad/h.

The FOM_1 values for some pure isotopes are shown in Table 1. The lower the criteria value, the better the quality of the material's barrier.

Table 1

FOM₁ values for some nuclear materials [1]

	²³³ U	²³⁵ U	²³⁸ Pu	²³⁹ Pu	²⁴⁰ Pu	²⁴¹ Pu	²⁴² Pu
FOM ₁	2.70	2.20	0.90	2.80	2.00	2.60	1.90

Isotopic benchmarking has also been used to evaluate the plutonium mixtures at the initial moment (RO discharge) and at the end of the fuel cycle (at 356th year). The used criteria are those for ²³⁸Pu concentration for low technology, defined by Kessler et al. and by Kimura et al. (1.6 wt. % and 2.0 wt. % respectively) [12, 13]. As an additional criterion the plutonium grades according to ²⁴⁰Pu weight fraction, as described by Pellaud in [19], are also used. Those criteria have been applied for assessment in a previous analysis [14].

The isotopic compositions, necessary for the assessment, have been calculated using the ORIGEN-ARP module of the SCALE6.1 system. The bare critical masses have been calculated using the KENO.V.a module of the same system [18]. The isotopic compositions for each fuel cycle stage have been calculated using the input data shown in Table 2. The critical masses have been calculated for each plutonium mixture for a homogenous sphere with density of 19.84 g/cm³, as it has been done in [15].

Table 2

Analysis input data

		UOX	MOX	MIX
²³⁵ U assay	wt. %	4.80	0.25	4.80
Plutonium mass fraction	wt. %	-	5.00	5.00
Fuel mass power load	MW/tHM	49.96	49.96	49.96
Irradiation duration per recycle	EFPD	1241.00	1241.00	1241.00

Results and discussion

The isotopic compositions of plutonium at the beginning and the end of the analysed fuel cycles are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3

Plutonium's isotopic vectors at the beginning and the end of the fuel cycles

t	UOX	UOX	MOX	MIX
	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%
t	0 yrs.	356 yrs.	356 yrs.	356 yrs.
²³⁸ Pu	3.581	0.280	0.298	0.688
²³⁹ Pu	47.706	58.507	39.544	24.992
²⁴⁰ Pu	24.414	30.164	37.309	32.341
²⁴¹ Pu	15.170	0.000	0.001	0.002
²⁴² Pu	9.128	11.049	22.847	41.977

It is evident that the plutonium from the discharged UOX fuel complies with the Kessler and Kimura criteria, which is not the case of the other isotopic mixtures. That is due to the fact that the half-life of ²³⁸Pu is 84.4 years which means that after 300 years of decay only about 8.5 % of the initial ²³⁸Pu nuclei would be present. Concerning the ²⁴⁰Pu fraction, the mixture in the discharged UOX fuel is reactor grade but is very close to the upper limit of 30 wt.%. All other mixtures are above the 30 wt.% threshold that defines the MOX plutonium grade.

Another observation is that the weight fraction of the odd isotopes declines from 62.877 wt.% in the year 0 to 58.507 wt.% in the 356th year of the once-through cycle, 39.545 wt.% at the end of the MOX cycle, and 24.994 wt.% at the end of the multiple recycle cycle, with ²⁴²Pu being the main isotope in the latter case. That illustrates the continuous deterioration of plutonium's isotopic composition caused by extended irradiation.

The results of the 'Figure of Merit' analysis are summarised in Tables 4, 5 and 6 with criteria values calculated for each stage of the fuel cycle. Table 7 shows a comparison of the FOM criteria values at the beginning and the end of each fuel cycle. The FOM values are similar to those obtained in previous analyses (e.g. in [14,15]). The summarised results show general improvement of the material barrier's qualities with exception of the no recycle case (when spontaneous neutron emission is not considered).

Table 4

Change of the FOM values at different stages of the multiple recycle fuel cycle

Stage	Year	FOM ₁	FOM ₂
Discharge R0	0	2.72	1.08
R0+10 (Load R1)	10	2.71	1.05
Discharge R1	14	2.61	0.78
R1+10 (Load R2)	24	2.60	0.73
Discharge R2	28	2.55	0.62
R2+10 (Load R3)	38	2.53	0.58
Discharge R3	42	2.55	0.58
R3+10 (Load R4)	52	2.50	0.52
Discharge R4	56	2.53	0.55
R4+1	57	2.53	0.55
R4+3	59	2.52	0.54
R4+10	66	2.50	0.51
R4+30	86	2.47	0.45
R4+100	156	2.45	0.40
R4+300	356	2.45	0.38

Table 5

Change of the FOM values at different stages of the once-through fuel cycle

Stage	Year	FOM ₁	FOM ₂
Discharge R0	0	2.72	1.08
R0+1	1	2.71	1.08
R0+3	3	2.71	1.07
R0+10	10	2.71	1.05
R0+30	30	2.71	1.01
R0+100	100	2.71	0.98
R0+300	300	2.71	0.97
R0+356	356	2.71	0.97

If the spontaneous neutron emission is not taken into account (the main effect of even plutonium isotopes) it is evident that the properties of plutonium's material barrier remain unchanged in the case of no recycle (Table 5). In the single recycle case there is a slight improvement in barrier's qualities over time, mainly due to the irradiation stage (Table 6). The same observations can be made in the multiple recycle case where the highest effect on the barrier's quality is observed (Table 5). Once again, the irradiation stages have higher impact. That influence however is highest after the first recycle stage and incrementally decreases with each following recycle. That is due to the deteriorating isotopic composition after each following recycle that limits the amount of burnt odd isotopes, thus limiting the impact on the barrier's quality. The circumstance that in the MIX fuel the plutonium is not the main source of fissile nuclei, unlike in MOX fuel, also contributes to that effect. Generally, it can be concluded that the impact of cooling time on material barrier's properties is relatively low. That supports the results published in [14].

Table 6

Change of the FOM values at different stages of the single recycle fuel cycle

Stage	year	FOM ₁	FOM ₂
Discharge R0	0	2.72	1.08
R0+10 (Load R1-MOX)	10	2.72	1.05
Discharge R1-MOX	14	2.64	0.82
R1-MOX+1	15	2.64	0.82
R1-MOX+3	17	2.63	0.80
R1-MOX+10	24	2.62	0.77
R1-MOX+30	44	2.60	0.71
R1-MOX+100	114	2.58	0.67
R1-MOX+300	314	2.59	0.66
R1-MOX+342	356	2.59	0.65

If the effects of the spontaneous neutron emission are taken into account, the barrier's quality improvement becomes much more pronounced. In that case, improvement occurs much faster and can be observed in all considered cases, the best effect again seen in the multiple recycle case. That is due to the higher weight fraction of even plutonium isotopes. Once again, irradiation has more pronounced effect than decay. The summary shown in Table 7 unequivocally shows the positive effect of multiple recycle on the qualities of plutonium's material barrier, with the spontaneous neutron emission having significant contribution.

Table 7

FOM values at the beginning and at the end of the fuel cycles

	UOX	MOX	MIX
FOM ₁ (t = 0 yrs.)	2.72	2.72	2.72
FOM ₂ (t = 0 yrs.)	1.08	1.08	1.08
FOM ₁ (t = 356 yrs.)	2.71	2.59	2.45
FOM ₂ (t = 356 yrs.)	0.97	0.65	0.38

The discrepancies between the results of isotopic benchmarking (non-compliance with the ²³⁸Pu fraction criteria) and the 'Figure of Merit' values (showing improved barrier quality) show the limitations of isotopic benchmarking, especially in the long-term analyses (good convergence in the short term has been demonstrated in [14]) and the need of applying more complex and reliable criteria in proliferation resistance analyses.

Conclusion

The present analysis has demonstrated that multiple recycling of plutonium is a viable option in terms of improving the quality of its material barrier to proliferation, especially in comparison with currently applied fuel cycle strategies. The limitations of isotopic benchmarking have also been demonstrated.

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Ivaylo Naydenov, PhD, Senior Assistant Professor, TU – Sofia, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, phone (+359) 898 59 71 94, e-mail: ivaylo.naydenov@gmail.com
Kalin Filipov, PhD, Associated Professor, TU – Sofia, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, phone (+359) 2 965 2297, e-mail: filipov@tu-sofia.bg